

EURODOC

contribution to the European Research Area

Eurodoc, 2017

Background

The *European Research Area (ERA)* is defined as a unified area open to the world, in which scientific knowledge, technology and researchers circulate freely.

ERA Stakeholder Platform

The European Commission (EC) considers that “[p]artnership is essential to complete ERA. The most effective and pragmatic approach for completing the European Research Area is a reinforced ERA partnership - deeper, wider and more efficient than to date - between Member States, the EC and research stakeholder organisations. This means complementing the primary ERA partnership between the Member States and the EC by systematically involving stakeholder organisations.”¹

The EC also states that “[t]he explicit role for research stakeholder organisations in the reinforced partnership for ERA is new and important. [...]. On the occasion of the adoption of the ERA Communication 'A Reinforced European Research Area Partnership for Excellence and Growth' on 17 July 2012, Commissioner Geoghegan-Quinn and five Stakeholder Organisations (SHOs) - European Association of Research and Technological Organisations (EARTO), European University Association (EUA), League of European Research Universities (LERU), NordForsk, Science Europe - signed a Joint Statement, four Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs), and accepted one Unilateral Statement in which SHOs undertook to work together towards the achievement of ERA by 2014. The EC set up a European Stakeholder Platform (ESP) to follow up on the implementation of the undertakings and offer SHOs a forum for discussion for the development of ERA policy.

This Stakeholder Platform is essential for the EC in order to implement ERA, as it gives the opportunity to the SHOs to interact not only with the EC but also amongst themselves, and to create partnership activities and enable consensus building. The Conference of European Schools for Advanced Engineering Education and Research (CESAER) joined the Stakeholder Platform on 17 July 2013 and handed over a Unilateral Statement to the EC. In this Joint Declaration, all organisations reaffirmed their joint commitment to achieving the goals of the European Research Area.

¹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/era/partnership_en.htm

Refocusing of ESP in 2016

Since 2015/2016, five additional organisations have been invited to attend the meetings of the platform as observers, in addition to the founding members. However, the Commissioner of Research, Science and Innovation, Carlos Moedas, announced new priorities in a Vision for Europe: "Open Innovation, Science, Open to the World" (3 O's).² New advisory structures were set up to support this new framework, in particular the "Open Science Policy Platform", and the ESP has recently been refocused on the monitoring of ERA implementation, in particular by Member States. In this context, discussions are underway on the formal continuation of the ESP and its potential successor. The EC is currently not expecting new submissions of ESP applications.

Eurodoc engagement

Eurodoc was invited to apply for membership to the ESP. Initial contacts for this purpose were formed by Eurodoc in 2015. The member organisations of Eurodoc supported Eurodoc applying for membership of the ESP, and after officially applying for membership, Eurodoc was invited by the EC to submit a comprehensive and detailed ERA strategy for Eurodoc.

The possibility of entering the platform is very interesting for Eurodoc in order to support the implementation of the ERA, which is one of the statutory goals of Eurodoc.³ NAs stresses that this would require a serious and continuous investment, not only from the Eurodoc administration, consisting of the Eurodoc board and Secretariat, but also from Eurodoc's members of national associations (NAs). The first draft of a Eurodoc ESP roadmap was discussed at the Eurodoc Annual General Meeting (AGM) in Luxembourg in 2016. The Eurodoc board received a mandate from Eurodoc's NAs to commit in the long term to the ESP and expressed their support and willing engagement in the ESP.

Eurodoc ERA Strategy

Eurodoc is committed, under Article 3 of its Statute, to contributing to ERA policies and to representing and creating a community of early-career researchers (ECRs) across Europe and in the EU political arena.

² <https://ec.europa.eu/research/openvision/index.cfm>

³ <http://eurodoc.net/wp-content/uploads/statutes15-en.pdf>

Eurodoc strives for all researchers, in particular doctoral candidates (DCs) and junior researchers (JRs), to be duly recognised and respected for the essential contributions they make to their research performing organizations (RPOs), to scientific advancement, and to civil society in general. This is also one of the core principles of the ERA European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers (C&C).⁴ Eurodoc fully supports the C&C.

Part A: Detailed presentation of Eurodoc

1. Nature of the organisation

Eurodoc is a non-party, non-profit, international, umbrella organisation representing the interests of national associations of early-career researchers in Europe.

Eurodoc is unique in its nature as a grassroots organisation which directly connects and represents ECRs across Europe. Eurodoc's members of NAs are, under its Statute, legal organisations which represent ECRs in a member state of the European Union and/or of the Council of Europe.

History

The need to establish a European-wide network of NAs representing ECRs was for the first time recognised in 2001, during a meeting of NAs representing ECRs at a conference in Uppsala. Following these efforts, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc) was officially founded in Girona, Spain, on February 2nd, 2002.

Eurodoc's scope extends, under Article 2 of its Statute, to the territory of all Member States of the European Union (EU) and the Council of Europe (CoE). Currently, Eurodoc has 32 members and 4 observers (see the section 4. Geographical distribution of affiliates across Europe).

2. Aim of the organisation

Eurodoc's aims according to Article 3 of its Statute are:

⁴ https://cdn2.euraxess.org/sites/default/files/brochures/am509774cee_en_e4.pdf

1. To represent doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level in matters of education, research and professional development of their careers.
2. To advance the quality of doctoral programmes and the standards of research activity in Europe.
3. To promote the circulation of information on issues regarding young researchers, organise events, take part in debates, and assist in the elaboration of policies about Higher Education and Research in Europe.
4. To establish and promote co-operation between national associations representing doctoral candidates and junior researchers within Europe. Eurodoc shall not interfere with the competences of its member organisations in respect of all national matters and issues.

The activities are focused on stakeholder representation of DCs and JRs across Europe and at the European level, working to create a community of DCS and JRs across Europe, contributing to ERA and EHEA policies, promoting a vision of ERA and EHEA where all researchers are duly recognised and respected for the essential contributions they make.”

3. Concrete actions implemented by the organisation

Eurodoc has always been deeply committed to the development of the ERA since it was established as a goal and EU policy priority. Eurodoc’s activities have consistently concentrated on supporting the ERA through implementing and promoting its fundamental principles and values.

Eurodoc ERA stakeholder activities

Since 2011, Eurodoc has actively participated in consultations of the EC and contributed to ERA development.

In 2011, Eurodoc issued a declaration of endorsement and commitment to the Recommendation of the European Commission on the European Charter for Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Re-

searchers⁵. Eurodoc strongly supports C&C implementation and encourages all NAs specifically and RPOs generally to endorse its principles.

In 2011/2012, Eurodoc issued a communication on EU Research and Innovation Funding which sketches a framework for a new generation of researchers (for FP8 and Horizon2020) and proposes seven recommendations towards better use of public funds for research and innovation at the EU level.⁶

On 13 September 2011, the ERA Committee (ERAC) held a stakeholder seminar to formally launch the public consultation on the ERA. Eurodoc participated in the meeting and highlighted several important issues for the ERA: (1) attracting non-EU researchers to the ERA, (2) recognising DCs of all nationalities as professionals, (3) removing barriers and helping researchers to be mobile in the EU, (4) improving the intersectoral mobility of ECRs between academia and the public/private sector, (5) highlighting the importance of and supporting the arts and humanities within the ERA. Each of these issues were subsequently released as *dedicated ERA consultation papers*.⁷

In 2015, Eurodoc conducted interviews with the European Parliament (EP) on the ERA. This study was used to improve the implementation of ERA policy at the EP.⁸

In 2015, Eurodoc provided input to the evaluation of the Innovation Union Flagship Initiative on ERA Framework - Quality of Doctoral Training. The evaluation was conducted by a consultancy in cooperation with the EC's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG R&I).

Eurodoc publications⁹

Eurodoc has produced two peer-reviewed research publications:

- Parada, Filomena & Peacock, John (2015) The Quality of Doctoral Training and Employability of Doctorate Holders. The Views of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers in Adrian Curaj,

⁵ <http://eurodoc.net/wp-content/uploads/2012/10/CC-endorsement-letter-Eurodoc-SIGNED-2.pdf>

⁶ http://eurodoc.net/wp-content/uploads/2012/10/2011_Eurodoc_Communication_FP8.pdf

⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/research/era/pdf/contributions/eurodoc-era-consultation_en.pdf

⁸ GIVE A LINK TO THIS STUDY

⁹ <http://eurodoc.net/policies>

Liviu Matei, Remus Pricopie, Jamil Salmi & Peter Scott (eds.) *The European Higher Education Area. Between Critical Reflections and Future Policies.*¹⁰

- Tan, Raoul & Dunja Potočnik (2006) Are You Experienced? Junior Scientists Should Make the Most of Opportunities to Develop Skills outside the Laboratory. *EMBO Reports* 7(10), pp. 961–964.¹¹

Eurodoc has published many *policy papers*:

- Recognising the Value and the Purpose of the Doctorate. Eurodoc's Recommendations (2017),
- Eurodoc Recommendations on the Entry and Residence of Third-Country Nationals for the Purpose of Research. Towards a More Adequate Framework (2015),
- Dual Career Opportunities for Doctoral Candidates and Early Career Researchers (2014),
- Journal Rankings and Interdisciplinarity (2014),
- Recommendations for Implementing Interdisciplinary Mobility (2013),
- Defining Doctoral Candidates and Doctoral Training (2012),
- Communication on a EU Research and Innovation Funding Framework for a New Generation of Researchers (2011),
- Recommendations for Admitting Non-EU Researchers (2010),
- European Career Framework (2010),
- Five Principles and Recommendations towards a More Open European Labour Market for Researchers (2008)
- Commentary on the Implementation of the "European Researcher's Partnership" (2008),
- Greenpaper on the Future of the European Research Area. Eurodoc Response on the Call for Consultation of the European Commission (2007),

¹⁰ <http://www.springer.com/gp/book/9783319187679>

¹¹ <http://doi.org/10.1038/sj.embor.7400811>

- Eurodoc Recommendation for Core Research Career Structures in Academia (2006),
- Recommendations on the Creation of an ERC (2005),
- The Strasbourg Declaration. Research Doctorates for the European Knowledge Society Conclusions and Recommendations (2005).

Eurodoc has also published statements on different issues crucial for higher education and research development:

- Eurodoc support statement on the "Open Letter on Recent Developments in Science in the US" (2017),
- Eurodoc statement "Brexit Should not Impact Open Academia!" (2016),
- Eurodoc statement "Open Access to Publications" (2015),
- Eurodoc support statement on the "Joint Declaration on Doctoral Training in Europe" (2014),
- Eurodoc statement "Visas for Iranian PhD Candidates in Norway" (2014).

Eurodoc has also regularly issued newsletters on the activities of its member NAs as well as important topics for ECRs since 2007.

Eurodoc conferences

Eurodoc's main events are the Eurodoc Annual Conference and AGM which have been held since 2002. These events are always held in different member countries and are supported by the local NA and academic communities. Each annual conference is structured around an important theme for ECRs, e.g. the conferences from the last 10 years were focused on the following:

- 2017, Oslo (Norway), "*Open Science. Challenges and Opportunities for Early Career Researchers*",
- 2016, Esch-sur-Alzette (Luxembourg), "*Early-Stage researchers' Training. Which Future?*",
- 2015, Cluj-Napoca (Romania), "*Empowering Young Researchers in Europe. Engagement and Participation*",

- 2014, Budapest (Hungary), "*The position of Early-Stage Researchers in ERA & EHEA. How to Face the Challenges Ahead?*",
- 2013, Lisbon (Portugal), "*Europe's Grand Societal Challenges. The Role of Early-Stage Researchers*",
- 2012, Krakow (Poland), "*Funding. How to Acquire Scientific Grants*",
- 2011, Vilnius (Lithuania), "*New Generation in Science. Toward a New Fashion ERA?*" *Unravelling Relationships between Research Traditions and New Generations' Hunger for Change*",
- 2010, Vienna (Austria), "*Stocktaking and Prospects. Doctoral Training and Research. The Link between EHEA and ERA*",
- 2009, Banská Bystrica (Slovakia), "*Innovation in Europe. From Academia to Practice and Back*",
- 2008, Fribourg (Switzerland), "*Excellence in Research from the Perspective of Young Researchers*", etc.

Eurodoc workshops

Eurodoc has also co-organised events which have been initiated and supported by member NAs:

- 2017, Debrecen (Hungary), "*International Workshop on Career Development and Interdisciplinarity for Early-Stage Researchers*", conducted within the international Spring Wind Conference and co-organised by Hungarian NA DOSz,
- 2016, Łódź (Poland), "*European Forum of Young Innovators (EFYI)*", co-organised by Poland Innovative Foundation and Polish NA KRD to bring together representatives from the worlds of science and business to discuss key issues affecting young innovators in Europe,
- 2015, public webinar on "*Open Access and the Opportunities raised for Early-Stage Researchers in a More Open Educational Environment*", co-organised by the Facilitate Open Science Training for European Research (FOSTER) project.

Eurodoc surveys

One of Eurodoc's main activities and unique strengths is direct communication with ECRs and ECR NAs across Europe as well as the ability to collect and analyse relevant data related to ECRs.

Eurodoc works to inform policy makers and other stakeholders of the situation facing ECRs. To perform this role efficiently Eurodoc conducts surveys and Annual Questionnaire (AQ) amongst its members. The AQ is not totally open to the public, it focuses both on internal aspects of Eurodoc (such as the internal structure of NAs and Eurodoc's goals), and on general ECR issues (such as doctoral training, career development, research policies, working conditions, mobility, ERA priorities, and the C&C).

Eurodoc has also conducted surveys on the contribution of its member NAs to ERA development in their respective countries. These surveys have usually focused on the development of more effective research systems and ECR representation, experience with and good practices in ERA policies, and the practice and promotion of the C&C in each country.¹²

Eurodoc issued the first Europe-wide survey on DCs in cooperation with the International Centre for Higher Education Research at the University of Kassel (2008-2009).¹³ In 2011, the results of the *Eurodoc Survey I* were published from the responses of 8900 DCs across Europe and shed light on many issues relevant for DCs. Of particular importance were the promotion and improvement of quality assurance in doctoral training and supervision, and how to ensure a successful transition from being a DC to a doctorate holder. The survey showed a clear need for doctoral training programmes to enhance the competencies necessary to succeed outside academia and for employers, especially in the non-academic sector, to understand and recognise the value of the doctorate.

Eurodoc has furthermore been involved in ECR surveys from the EC and other higher education and research stakeholders:

- Open Science & Career Development for Researchers survey from the EC (2017),
- SuperProfDoc survey from a consortium of stakeholders (2016),

¹² http://eurodoc.net/wp-content/uploads/Eurodoc_Newsletter_N20_Oct2016.pdf
http://eurodoc.net/wp-content/uploads/2012/07/Eurodoc_survey_I_report_2011.pdf

- International Mobility of Researchers Working outside of Europe survey from the EC (2012).

4. Geographical distribution of affiliates across Europe – list of affiliates/partners

Eurodoc has 32 members and 4 observers (see figure 1).

Fig.1. Eurodoc geographical coverage

Eurodoc consists of 23 EU members:

- Austria (Austrian Students' Union, Österreichische HochschülerInnenschaft, ÖH),
- Belgium (Focus Research),

- Bulgaria (Association of Doctoral Candidates in Bulgaria, ADCB),
- Croatia (Young Scientists Network, MLAZ),
- Cyprus (Association of PhD Candidates of Cyprus, CESRA),
- Czech Republic (SKRVŠ, Student Chamber of the Council of HEIs, SKRVŠ),
- Denmark (PhD Network, PhDNettet),
- Finland (Finnish Union of University Researchers and Teachers, FUURT),
- France (Confederation of Young Researchers, Confédération des Jeunes Chercheurs CJC),
- Germany (Thesis – Interdisciplinary Network for Doctoral Candidates and Early Stage Researchers),
- Hungary (Association of Hungarian PhD and DLA Students (DOSz),
- Italy (Italian Association of PhD Candidates and Early Stage Researchers, Associazione Dottorandi e Dottori di Ricerca Italiani, ADI),
- Latvia (Association of Latvian Young Scientists, LJZA),
- Lithuania (Lithuanian Society of Young Researchers, LSJR),
- Luxembourg (LuxDoc a.s.b.l. – LuxDoc),
- The Netherlands (PhD Candidates Network of the Netherlands, PNN),
- Poland (National Representation of PhD Candidates in Poland, KRDP),
- Portugal (Portuguese Association of Grant-Holding Researchers, ABIC),
- Slovakia (Slovak PhD Students' Association, ADS),
- Slovenia (Society of Young Researchers Slovenia, DMRS),
- Spain (Federacion de Jovenes Investigadores, FJI-Precarios),
- Sweden (National Student Union of Sweden, SFS-dk),
- United Kingdom (National Postgraduate Committee, NPC).

There are 2 European Free Trade Association (EFTA) members:

- Norway (Association of Doctoral Organisations in Norway, SiN),
- Switzerland (actionuni).

There are 3 associated EU members:

- Macedonia (Union of Young Researchers of Macedonia, UYRM),
- Serbia (Doktoranti Srbije),
- Iceland (Association of Doctoral Candidates and Doctoral Graduates, FeDoN).

There are 3 Eastern Partnership (EaP) members:

- Ukraine (Young Scientists Council under the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, RMU),
- Azerbaijan (Azerbaijan Young Scientists, Post-Graduates, and Masters Union, AYSPMU),
- Moldova (Moldovan Association of Young Researchers, PRO-Science).

There is one non-EU affiliated member:

- Russia (The Russian Union of Young Scientists, RoSMU).

The 4 observers are 2 individual and 2 organisations. The 2 individual observers are Turkey and Bosnia Herzegovina. The organisations are Ro-Doc from Romania and YSDCG from Georgia.

5. Internal structuring of the organisation

Eurodoc's organisational structure consists, under Article 9 of its Statute, of four main bodies (see figure 2):

- a) The General Meeting – Eurodoc's highest decision-making body. Consists of delegates from each member NA. Some of its exclusive competencies include modifications of the Statute, election of administration members, approval and monitoring of the budget, approval and monitoring of activities of the administration, and acceptance and rejection of member NAs.

Fig.2 Eurodoc organizational structure

- b) An Administrative Board - Eurodoc's regular executive body. Represents, leads, and administrates Eurodoc according to guidelines set by the General Meeting. The Administrative Board is elected by the General Meeting and consists of a President, Vice-President, Treasurer, Secretary, and up to three General Board Members, all of whom must be affiliated with a Eurodoc member NA. Eurodoc strives for diversity of representation.
- c) A Secretariat – Elected by the General Meeting to achieve the objectives of Eurodoc. May include a Secretariat Coordinator, Working Group Coordinators, and other Officers. Each Working Group focuses on a specific theme and provides input on which Eurodoc is able to advise and make policy for its member NAs. Other Officers usually include a Policy Officer, Social Media and Newsletter Coordinator, and Webmaster for the Eurodoc website.

- d) An Advisory Board and Board of Trustees – The Advisory Board acts as a support for the organisation and provides the Administrative Board with solicited and unsolicited advice. It also facilitates the knowledge transfer between Administrative Board and contributes to the continuity of Eurodoc as an organisation. The Board of Trustees oversees the general activities of Eurodoc and typically consists of recognised individuals who are involved with topics related to ECRs, the ERA, and the EHEA.

6. Eventual working groups related to RDI

Eurodoc employs a number of Working Groups (WG) which are chaired by WG Coordinators and deal with a specific topic related to ECRs, the ERA, and the EHEA. The WGs typically deal with the topics of employment and career development, diversity and gender equality, interdisciplinarity, mobility, doctoral training, and more recently the various aspects of Open Science for ECRs. The members of the WGs usually consist of members of individual NAs as well as other specialists.

Employment & Career Development WG

The current WG Employment & Career Development focuses on promoting and monitoring the employment status and conditions of ECRs as well as the career development and opportunities for ECRs in Europe. The WG is at the centre of Eurodoc mission to envision and promote the ERA and the EHEA where all researchers are duly recognised and respected for the essential contributions that they make. The basic guideline for the actions of the WG is provided by C&C from the EC.

The focus of the WG has usually been both on DCs and JRs. However, the recent growth in the number of postdoctoral researchers across Europe, and the difficulties they face in accessing adequate employment and working conditions, led Eurodoc to recently emphasise this group of ECRs within the framework of the WG.

Current actions of the WG focus on promoting the benefits of long-term or permanent (research) contracts in different career options, promoting an international labour market for ECRs, monitoring conditions of recruitment, working contracts and international mobility, and monitoring the challenges of academic employment and career development (so-called "academic bottlenecks") in different member NA states.

Members of the working group take part in public discussions on these matters in different national and international events and forums, such as by the European Association for Research on Learning and Instruction (EARLI), the European Forum of Young Innovators (EFYI), and Science Europe workshops.

Gender Equality WG

Eurodoc is committed to promoting and advancing the fair and equitable inclusion of people of diverse backgrounds, including sex, race, ethnicity, nationality, religion, sexual identity, culture, disability, and others, in their careers as ECRs and moving into their subsequent careers in and outside academia. The WG Gender Equality is dedicated to this cause and conducts research, policy proposals, and initiatives on gender equality.

The main objective of the WG is to promote and advance a fair and equitable inclusion of women and men in their careers, both as ECRs and their subsequent careers in academia, industry, and other social spheres. The WG also focuses on managing policies and initiatives related to this task and collaborating with associations and organisations that have similar interests to create mutually beneficial relationships.

In 2012, the WG conducted a survey among its members to gather statistical data about gender equality in the PhD process. A relative equality was found during the PhD. After the PhD, a “leaking pipeline” phenomenon, i.e. a major leave of women from academia, was observed: academic careers seemed less attractive for women. As a consequence, there is an under-representation of women in academia.

WG members have participated in gender equality conferences, such as the SAPGERIC conference in Vilnius (2013). WG members have also collaborated with organisations like GenderSTE and participate in meetings GenderSTE General Meeting in Heraklion (2014) and in Lisbon (2015).

The WG plans to expand its activities on diversity for ECRs in the future and focus on dual careers, diversity in leadership and board positions, sexual harassment in academia, and gender equality in STEM disciplines.

Interdisciplinarity WG

Eurodoc comprises ECRs of many different disciplinary and cultural backgrounds and is therefore ideally positioned to promote discussion about the future of disciplinary configuration and interdisciplinary collaboration inside and outside academia. Interdisciplinarity studies and research are

crucial in solving some of the most complex issues in contemporary societies. The Interdisciplinarity WG's members come from various disciplines, such as chemistry, economy, philosophy and mathematics.

The strategic aim of the WG Interdisciplinarity is to improve dialogue and join forces with other NAs to create an interdisciplinary research community. This online European platform facilitates interdisciplinary and international scientific exchange and collaboration. WG members have participated in various national and European events on interdisciplinarity. Active members of the WG monitor major publications and scientific research in the field of interdisciplinary studies and keep the WG up to date on the state of the art in the field.

Mobility WG

The WG Mobility has been active since the beginning of Eurodoc and aims to promote the mobility of ECRs in Europe. The activities of the WG involve identifying barriers and proposing solutions to the moving of researchers from one institution to another, from one sector to another, and from one region to another in Europe. Its members have actively participated in many national and European events as well as consulting on and producing policy related to the mobility of ECRs.

The current focus of the WG is on intersectoral mobility, with emphasis on the needs of ECRs and helping the transition from academia to the public/private sector. The goals of the WG are to disseminate the state of play of intersectoral mobility in Europe, to address potential barriers to intersectoral mobility, and to propose best practices and policy advice for all European stakeholders. Also of current importance are the potential consequences for the mobility of ECRs following a Brexit.

The WG Mobility has engaged in national and European events as well as publishing position and policy papers on mobility. WG members have also consulted with the ERA on mobility policy for ECRs. The WG is now working with the EC on a survey on Open Science and Career Development of Researchers and aims to interpret mobility in Open Science.

Open Access WG

The aims of the Open Access WG are to raise awareness and spread knowledge of Open Access, Open Science, and the debate on 'openness' in general, among ECRs. Therewith, young researchers get an understanding of scholarly communication and publishing as key factors in the

research system. In this sense, a focus of the WG is on advocating the advantages of Open Access and informing about the different routes and their implications, benefits, and barriers for ECRs. Moreover, WG members can link to their NAs and thematic communities and can encourage an informed debate. The WG also serves for network building for ECRs interested in Open Access policies and to make ECRs aware of the benefits of Open Access publishing.

Continuous activities of the WG consist of information sharing among ECRs on Open Access and liaising with stakeholders in the field of Open Access and Open Science. This includes promoting events which are of interest to ECRs, e.g. the international conference OpenCon (organised by SPARC), and liaising with projects on Open Science training, such as FOSTER (FP7 project) where Eurodoc is engaged in the Advisory Board.

Recently in 2015, the WG released a statement on Eurodoc's position on Open Access to publications. The WG also organised a webinar together with the FOSTER project on "Open Access and Early-Stage Researchers. Challenges and Opportunities".

PhD Training WG

The PhD Training WG is a new WG and is important for the future careers of PhD holders. Unfortunately, recommendations from key documents on doctoral training reforms have not been widely implemented across Europe. Especially important is to link doctoral training not only with academic but also with working life. The main aim of the WG is to promote good practices of PhD training from different contexts in Europe and to help with the implementation of recommendations from key documents. Other core goals of the WG aim to:

- a) Collect and share good practices of doctoral training in Europe, especially with regards to transferable skills (sharing documents, regulations, proposals, statements),
- b) Provide documentation on these practices to individuals and to NAs by creating an online platform on this topic,
- c) Define recommendations on PhD training to ensure quality and adequacy of training of PhD candidates and to promote the recognition of the PhD as a professional experience,
- d) Share and support the "Principles for Innovative Doctoral Training" and "Salzburg I and II recommendations",

- e) Produce a policy paper on best practices and policy advice aimed at EU institutions, which also identifies factors that facilitate or hinder the diffusion of transferable skills,
- f) Initiate pilot projects to foster PhD training outside of academia in industry and public/private organisations and stimulate entrepreneurship among PhD candidates.

New recommendations on doctoral training are crucial so that ECRs are adequately prepared for their careers and have the necessary competence to deal with new societal transformations.

7. Recent and ongoing projects related to RDI

Eurodoc has taken part in many projects as a partner or advisory board member. Aside from Eurodoc's own surveys on ECRs (as mentioned above), Eurodoc has also contributed to the groundbreaking European University Association (EUA) projects *DOC-CAREERS I* (2006-2008)¹⁴ and *DOC-CAREERS II* (2009-2012)¹⁵. The first project explored the relations between doctoral programmes and the career development and employability prospects for DCs. The second project was conceived as an exploratory action to test the feasibility of regional workshops as an instrument to foster collaboration between university and industry.

Eurodoc was a partner in the *DocLinks Project - Increasing Understanding and Establishing Better Links between African and European Doctoral Education Candidates* (2012-2013). ACU has been awarded a grant by the European Commission, EACEA Erasmus Mundus Programme to implement a two-year project on promoting networking between African and European doctoral candidates and early career researchers. The project *Increasing Understanding and Establishing Better Links between African and European Doctoral Education Candidates (DocLinks)* will enhance mutual understanding through the creation of a unique network and website bringing together African and European research students. Eurodoc was involved as a steering and working group member and helped develop and spread surveys among ECRs.

¹⁴ <http://www.eua.be/eua-work-and-policy-area/research-and-innovation/doctoral-education/doc-careers>

¹⁵ <http://www.eua.be/activities-services/projects/past-projects/research-and-innovation/doc-careers-ii.aspx>

Eurodoc participated in the ad hoc group on the third cycle of the *Bologna Follow-Up Group (BFUG)*. The ad hoc group on the third cycle has been set up by the BFUG in 2012 to contribute to the realization of the plan of work for the period 2012 – 2015. The group is included as sub – sub structure of the Structural Reforms Working Group. The mandate of the group was to (1) map the current implementation of the third cycle in the EHEA, in the light of the “Salzburg II recommendations” and the Principles for Innovative Doctoral Training; (2) formulate policy proposals to promote quality, transparency, employability and mobility in the third cycle, on the basis of the outcomes of the previous point and taking into account the developments foreseen within the ERA by Horizon 2020 and other EU initiatives; (3) formulate policy proposals to improve the transition between the second and the third cycle, with the aim to strengthen the link between education and research.

Eurodoc was a partner in the *PromoDoc project* (2010-2013), funded by the EC in the framework of the Erasmus Mundus Action 3 (EM A3) programme, and focused on the promotion of European higher education at the doctoral level. The project aimed to showcase the attractiveness of doctoral studies in Europe, to improve awareness of opportunities for doctoral studies, to facilitate access to European doctoral programmes among students in third-world countries, especially in the industrialised countries and territories of Canada, Hong Kong, Japan, Singapore, South Korea, Taiwan, and the USA. The PromoDoc Consortium aims, by combining information tools and international events, to give momentum to the further promotion of European doctoral studies in the future.¹⁶

Eurodoc was an associated partner for the *Universities in the Knowledge Economy (UNIKE) project*, a four-year collaborative project funded by the EU FP7 through the Marie Curie Actions.¹⁷ The project, an Initial Training Network (ITN), started in 2012 and involves 6 universities, 6 full partners located in Europe, and other associated partners from public and private organisations. The aim of UNIKE was to train a network of researchers aiming to produce original research on the changing roles and scope of universities in the global knowledge economies, with a focus on Europe and the Asia-Pacific Rim regions.

¹⁶ <http://www.promodoc.eu/institutions-project>

¹⁷ <http://unike.au.dk>

Between 2013 and 2015 Eurodoc was a regular contributor to the *Science Europe* WG on Research Careers. Eurodoc participated in the Workshop “Researchers’ Careers: Postdoctoral Schemes and Intersectoral Mobility Schemes”. At the Workshop were publicly presented the findings and recommendations of the Working Group (WG) on Research Careers concerning the current situation for funding schemes in Europe aimed at postdoctoral researchers and intersectoral mobility. Moreover, Eurodoc contributed to the report on the postdoctoral funding schemes in Europe.¹⁸ Eurodoc remains in contact with Science Europe and plans to continue cooperating with Science Europe on ECR-related issues.

Eurodoc is currently a partner in the *Erasmus+ SuperProfDoc project*¹⁹, conducted from the 2014 to the 2017 and is funded through the Erasmus+ programme KA2 (project number 2014-1-UK01-KA203-001629). The project aims at defining the best practices of supervision for what can be called “professional doctorates” and “industrial doctorates” when a research project is developed in a non-academic context. The outcome of the project will consist of appropriate resources (workshop, examiner list, handbook, and social media) for European universities, research institutions, and companies to use the innovation and new knowledge created from the project.

Eurodoc is also contributing to the *SAF21 project*, focused on EU fisheries, to develop effective fisheries management strategies.²⁰ The research and development will be undertaken by a group of social scientists, managed by the SAF21 consortium, a mix of academic and commercial organisations. Of particular interest to Eurodoc is the way the research and training programme is structured (practical, collaborative approach to learning, combining research with developing business management skills through placements and training).

Eurodoc will join the Policy Advisory Panel of the *Promoting Integrity as an Integral Dimension of Excellence in Research (PRINTEGER) project*.²¹ This project is funded by the EU in the framework of Horizon2020. Its mission is to enhance research integrity by promoting a research culture

¹⁸ <http://www.scienceeurope.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/20160922-Survey-Postdocs-Final.pdf>

¹⁹ <http://superprofdoc.eu>

²⁰ <http://www.saf21.org>

²¹ <https://printeger.eu>

in which integrity is part and parcel of what it means to do excellent research and not just an external and restrictive control system. To promote such a culture, an improved governance of integrity and responsible research has to be informed by practice: the daily operation of researchers and the tensions of a complex research system.

8. Motivation(s) of Eurodoc to join the ERA Platform

Eurodoc is motivated to join the ESP by its statutory goals, under Article 3 of its Statute, which are to represent DCs and JRs at the European level in matters of education, research, and professional development of their careers, and to promote the circulation of information on issues regarding ECRs, organise events, take part in debates, and assist in the elaboration of policies about Higher Education and Research in Europe.

At present, despite efforts of over more than a decade to develop a single ERA and EHEA, there still exist strong discrepancies in how ECRs are treated throughout Europe and across disciplines. DCs and JRs should be fully recognised as professional workers. As such, they deserve *appropriate working conditions and the recognition of their role in policy debates* at their respective institutions, at all levels of governance, and in all policy circles where such debates are taking place.

In particular, DCs and JRs working in academia should be recognised as a vital part of the Higher Education Institution's (HEI) "work-force", given their major role in the research and teaching environments, and in the long-term sustainability and success of the HEIs. Similarly, employers and funders outside academia should recognise that PhD holders are an added value to their workforce as highly skilled professionals with research experience. The work of DCs and JRs *should be granted with adequate funding, social security and mobility rights*.

In 2011, Eurodoc declared a commitment to ERA to support and fully endorse its principles and initiatives. Eurodoc not only endorses the C&C, but has also contributed to its development, and most of Eurodoc's actions are devoted to the principles in the C&C. Moreover, Eurodoc believes that researchers, employers, and funders should work together to ensure that the C&C is fully and properly implemented and promoted.

Eurodoc further supports other policy initiatives that fit the ERA such as mobility, transparency in recruitment, and the value and purpose of the

doctorate. To sum up, Eurodoc focuses not only on the implementation of ERA policies but crucially also on shaping ERA policies through constructively representing the interests of ECRs. This is a mandate which Eurodoc uniquely is able to uphold as the voice of ECRs in Europe.

Part B: Meeting the 5 criteria for membership

Eurodoc meets all membership criteria for the ESP, in particular representativeness, critical mass to foster ERA implementation, and strong relationship to research and innovation (R&I).

1. *A strong relationship to Research and Innovation*

Eurodoc is an organisation for and by ECRs. Policies concerning R&I directly affect the daily lives of our member NAs and ECRs. Most of the research of RPOs is conducted by ECRs, and ECRs therefore contribute in a significant manner to the research output of RPOs and to innovation in society in general. Eurodoc member NAs are also strongly committed to ERA implementation and Eurodoc monitors and shares their good practices.²² Eurodoc itself and its activities are thus synonymous with R&I and Eurodoc provides a crucial stakeholder role in advising on R&I.

Research and scientific communication is international in its basic understanding and is becoming increasingly so. Open Access and Open Data, as well as Open Science in general, have become a key issue in scientific practice and communication. Open Science enables researchers, regardless of discipline and location, to access research outputs everywhere and enables worldwide collaboration of the research community. ECRs play a crucial role, both as DCs and JRs but also as the senior researchers of the future, in adopting and practicing Open Science. The future of Open Science and R&I is clearly in the hands of ECRs.

Eurodoc and its WGs focus on the exchange of innovative best practices in different areas of academic activities, starting from doctoral training to career development and interdisciplinary research. Moreover, Eurodoc is a platform for NAs to improve their organisational capacities, transferring European practices and priorities onto national organisations. Eurodoc's

²² http://eurodoc.net/wp-content/uploads/Eurodoc_Newsletter_N20_Oct2016.pdf

WGs focus typically on issues such as the mobility, career development, and training of ECRs. These topics are intrinsically linked to R&I and Eurodoc is thus an important driver and facilitator of R&I.

2. A critical mass to foster ERA implementation

Eurodoc membership comprises 32 NAs, plus incidental observers, from countries all across Europe. Eurodoc works together with its member NAs to raise awareness and promote the implementation of ERA policies at the national level. Eurodoc not only reaches existing ECRs, but continuously reaches beginning ECRs, which is crucial to the ongoing effort to raise awareness among ECRs of the ERA.

Eurodoc's member NAs are characterised by different types of memberships, which reflects the diversity of higher education systems and research careers, as well as labour markets across Europe. Some NAs only allow individual ECRs to be members and some only allows organisations representing ECRs in the respective country to be members. Another organisations, in turn, allow individual ECR members from the respective country. Eurodoc's remaining member NAs are open to both individual and organisation members.

Eurodoc, through its member NAs and their members, is in touch with and represents a vast majority of the community of ECRs in Europe. Eurodoc is thus the ideal stakeholder to represent and communicate with ECRs in the implementation of ERA principles.

3. Representativeness (e.g. leader in a field)

Eurodoc is the only grassroots organisation that specifically aims to represent and build a European-wide community among ECRs. Eurodoc is de facto the voice of ECRs all across Europe, and represents DCs (R1 researchers) and JRs (R2 researchers), from all across Europe in both EU and CoE territory.

Representativeness of ECRs is ensured by the very structure of Eurodoc's organisation. The member NAs are not only members of Eurodoc but are collectively the highest decision-making body in the organisation. The Eurodoc administration simply carries out the wishes of the member NAs. The member NAs, in turn, consist of individual ECR members and organi-

sations, and are all active at a national level in their respective countries. This unique structure of Eurodoc ensures that Eurodoc is fully representative of ECRs in Europe and that Eurodoc is a fully mandated and vital stakeholder in representing ECRs at a European level.

4. Ability to cover a number of relevant ERA priorities/actions in its mandate to formally commit to the realisation of ERA

Eurodoc is fully able to cover ERA priorities.

4.1 More effective national research systems

Eurodoc and its members have the ability and legal mandate to make a contribution to making the national research systems more effective. Though established and leading researchers are the drivers of research, ECRs are the main workforce of the research system. The latter cannot be totally effective if they are not adequately trained and rewarded. Eurodoc is thus in agreement with ERA principles that researchers should be recognised and rewarded for their valuable contribution, and strives for all ECRs to be adequately trained, recognised, and remunerated.

Eurodoc's members are all engaged in improving their national research systems and share their best practices with each other. Eurodoc further attempts to improve national research systems as an active stakeholder on a European level and is fully engaged in policy advice and contributes to crucial discussions on ECRs with major stakeholders such as the EC, the EUA, Science Europe, Euroscience, LERU, and the Guild.

4.2 Jointly addressing grand challenges (optimal transnational cooperation and competition)

Eurodoc addresses grand challenges in Europe both as a pan-European representative of ECRs at an EU level and in the form of its member NAs who represent ECRs in their own countries. Eurodoc's activities are consistently focused on ERA and EHEA policies and Eurodoc aims, through active participation and constructive discourse with education and research stakeholders, to improve the position and conditions for ECRs.

Eurodoc encourages transnational collaboration among its member NAs and supports information exchange and joint actions. Eurodoc is constantly in contact with its member NAs and encourages discussion

amongst its NAs. Eurodoc brings its various NAs physically together for its General Meetings, where contacts between countries are strengthened and new collaborations arise. Eurodoc also has rich experience in jointly addressing grand challenges through its various WGs on ERA and EHEA topics such as training, professional development, and mobility of ECRs.

Eurodoc also has a history (as shown above) with jointly addressing grand challenges with major stakeholders in the ERA and EHEA fields. Prime examples are Eurodoc's fruitful cooperation with the EUA on surveys for ECRs and with Science Europe on ECR career development. Eurodoc's current cooperation with the SGHRM at the EC on Open Science is a further testament to Eurodoc's willingness to jointly address issues facing ECRs.

4.3 Effective investment in and use of research infrastructures (optimal transnational cooperation and competition)

Eurodoc members come from different European countries who are interested in working at the national and European level. Thus implemented transnational cooperation and exchange of information on cross-disciplinary research on the national research systems.

4.4 An open labour market for researchers

Eurodoc is committed to raising awareness about and promoting the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R), the Human Resources Excellence Logo, and the principles of the C&C from the EC. Eurodoc fully endorses the C&C and pays special attention to issues of the open labour market. Eurodoc's member NA's support the C&C and push for transparent and open recruitment processes at their own national level. Eurodoc is also committed to promoting the EURAXESS jobs portal and ensuring the mobility of ECRs across Europe.

Many of Eurodoc's activities focus on the open labour market and are carried out in its specialised WGs such as the WG for Mobility of ECRs, the WG for Employment and Career Development of ECRs, and the WG for PhD Training. The Mobility WG, in particular, aims to identify barriers and provide solutions to mobility of ECRs. Both the Employment and Career Development WG and the PhD Training WG, amongst other priorities, aim to provide ECRs with the adequate skills they need to be mobile in their careers. This mobility is geographical, sectoral, and disciplinary.

An additional issue for Eurodoc is the consequences of mobility: ECRs who move often must decide to postpone starting a family or moving their families with them. Eurodoc encourages its members to be mobile but at the same time raises awareness of the difficulties ECRs face when being mobile. Such issues include daily activities such as finding a job for partners, finding good childcare facilities, schools for children, and language barriers. By addressing these issues, Eurodoc aims to help in opening up the labour market both generally and specifically to its ECRs.

4.5 Gender equality and gender mainstreaming in research

Eurodoc is fully aware of the importance of gender equality issues. Eurodoc is committed to promoting and advancing fair and equal chances of women and men to follow a career in science, be it as a DC, JR, or at any other career level. Eurodoc takes advantage of its international composition to survey the situation from different countries, and exchange ideas and good practices from all over Europe, in order to raise awareness.

Eurodoc supports activities that engage in debates on and projects actively promoting gender equality, both through the Gender Equality WG and as a support for its member NAs. All Eurodoc WGs, in fact, pay particular attention to the issues of female researchers and gender equality in education and research. Eurodoc attempts to be gender balanced in its own internal administration, especially in the Administrative Board and Secretariat. Eurodoc further encourages its members to celebrate the International Day of Women and Girls in Science.

4.6 Optimal transfer, access to and circulation of scientific knowledge (Open Science and Open innovation)

Eurodoc fully supports the Open Science movement and pays particular attention to Open Access and Open Data for ECRs. Eurodoc has continually raised awareness for Open Science in discussions among its members, in its newsletters, and by promoting Open Access policies in its communication with members. The topic of Eurodoc's coming annual conference in Oslo in 2017 is, in fact, Open Science and Eurodoc members will openly engage in discussion with specialists on Open Science and share issues with and best practices for Open Science.²³ Eurodoc is furthermore currently participating in the WG Skills under SGHRM as is

²³ <http://eurodoc-oslo2017.org>

actively cooperating on a survey on Open Science and Career Development for Researchers (as mentioned above).

Eurodoc's Open Access WG focuses, furthermore, specifically on disseminating best practices and promoting the publishing of ECR research outputs in Open Access journals and repositories. Eurodoc is planning to further expand the scope of this WG to the various aspects of Open Science in general.

4.7. International cooperation (openness to the world)

International cooperation is an essential and inherent aspect of Eurodoc's organisation. Eurodoc brings together 36 countries (members and observers). Eurodoc is governed by the international board according to principles of participatory democracy and its activities are fully transparent to all of its members. Eurodoc further supports its members in international exchange and cooperation. Eurodoc's members are in constant dialogue with each other but also with respective stakeholders from their own countries. Eurodoc operates thus openly in its own structure and effectively encourages openness and international collaboration among ECRs all across Europe.

5. Added value to the existing partnership and no duplication or disagreement/conflict concerning commitments.

The value of Eurodoc for the ERA Stakeholders' Platform is that Eurodoc is the de facto representative of ECRs in Europe. Its unique organisation and representation gives Eurodoc an official mandate to be the voice of ECRs in Europe and also to act as a liaison between major stakeholders and ECRs.

This network of national organisations of doctoral candidates and junior researchers in European countries is able to promote ERA values, C&C principles, research integrity, and the strategic goals of Horizon2020 among academic communities of ECRs from the inside. Eurodoc is perfectly placed thus to not only as a stakeholder transferring the opinions of ECRs to the ESP, but also to transfer important issues and principles from the ESP to ECRs.

To sum up, Eurodoc is a valuable stakeholder for the ESP in uniquely representing and communicating with ECRs in Europe.

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More information is provided at: www.eurodoc.net

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